

Report of the 6th International Association Strikes and Social Conflicts Conference

6th Conference in Cape Town, South Africa from 4-7 February 2024. The conference was organised around the theme, "Strike Activity in the 21st Century: Implications of the Recent Global Upsurge" considering the strikes and protests which spread across the world since the Arab Spring of the early 2010s. The objective of the conference was to explore the nature, dynamics, trajectory, limits and potential, and implications of strikes and protests of the 21st century. The conference solidarity partners, the Rosa Luxemburg Stiftung (Southern Africa) and Lo-Norway had made a meaningful subsidy to ensure a successful and dynamic conference. More importantly the conference took place in the context of global protests against the genocide in Palestine and the case brought by South Africa to the International Court of Justice against Israel.

INTEREST IN THE CONFERENCE

As the 2022 conference in Rotterdam mainly drew interest from Europe, the members meeting agreed that the conference in South Africa would target 70 people and would ensure more representation from countries of the Global South. An initial total of 47 abstracts were received with 62 participants. Due to the inflationary spiral in the second half of 2023 combined with budget cuts of university faculties many participants especially from the Global South withdrew their participation from the conference with some provision made for online presentations. Interest in the conference came from;

Kenya, Nigeria, Ethiopia, Zimbabwe, Mozambique, South Africa, Philippines, Brazil, India, Uruguay, Mexico, Columbia, Portugal, UK, USA, Belgium, Germany, Italy, Spain, Turkey and Finland.

In the final programme the presenters came from; Zimbabwe, South Africa, Mexico, Philippines, India, Columbia, Argentina, US, Portugal, UK, Germany, Spain and Holland. The total number of participants of the conference including walk-ins was about 60 people.

ASSESSING THE QUALITY OF THE CONFERENCE PRESENTATIONS

On the basis of the collective judgement of the conference organising team and feedback provided at the Association's general meeting, as well as more informally, the quality of conference presentations was very high throughout. This was evident in the broad range of strikes and social conflicts that were explored within different countries globally, across both historical and contemporary times frames, and often of a comparative nature; the combination of both (with varying balance of emphasis) extensive analytical and empirical dimensions within each contribution; and the wide variety of scholar-

ly methodological approaches adopted and justified. In the process, across the different scheduled sessions there was extensive evidence of probing questions, reflections, argument and debate, further enlivening and enriching conference proceedings. The presentations revealed that labour is not on an eternal downward spiral and that gains including labour reforms indicate that labour is engaged in a fightback in both the Global South and the Global North.

MOVING FORWARD

The International Association Strikes and Social Conflicts (IASSC) is now in a new phase of its international profile and growth thanks to those who participated, its long-standing members and new solidarity partners. The diversity of the conference participants, the high quality of the presentations and engagement which all point to an overall direction in assisting progressive struggles, and the forging of a new discourse as we enter a new historical phase of global capitalism and geo-political change.

The IASSC board agreed to hold the next conference in Baltimore, USA in September 2025 ■